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FROM TRAINING TO PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: A STUDY BASED ON THE SOCIAL PROJECT FOR PSYCHO- PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION (PROSIPP) DEVELOPED AT THE FRANCISCAN INSTITUTE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN PAÇO DO LUMIAR, MA

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ABSTRACT

The case study carried out at the Franciscan Higher Education Institute (IESF) deals with the relevance of psychopedagogy and continuing training for the psychopedagogues taking part in the Social Project for Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp).